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Research Article

**“JOB RELATED BURNOUT MANAGEMENT AMONG
NURSES” IN CARDIAC ICU****¹Huma Bano, ²Ms. Sana Sehar, ³Muhammad Afzal, ⁴Dr. Syed Amir Gilani.**

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Article Received: September 2019 **Accepted:** October 2019 **Published:** November 2019**Abstract:**

Burnout, depression, low job satisfaction level effect on nurses performance badly. I have been observed multiple time that the staff nurses of ICU does not take interest to pay attention towards their duties as honestly and passionately as their profession demand to be. whereas, the other thing which was observed they were not concern how the negligence of duty performance impact on the recovery of cardiac patient who need more intensive care after heart surgeries. Staff nurses of every shift makes dispute on handed and taking over the patient. In this regard a study conducted in Iran on the “Predictors of happiness among Iranian Nurses” which result show by multiple regression analysis that there is a strong correlation with self-actualization and self-esteem with job satisfaction and happiness

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INTRODUCTION:**Situation / Incident:**

From the last couple of the weeks I have been observed and noted that the working environment seems tense, as nurses are burning out due to multiple work related problems, for instance, work overload, performing and spending too much time in non-nursing task, lack of performance appraisal, lack of coherence, poor interpersonal relationship among staff etc.

Burnout, depression, low job satisfaction level effect on nurses performance badly. I have been observed multiple time that the staff nurses of ICU does not take interest to pay attention towards their duties as honestly and passionately as their profession demand to be. whereas, the other thing which was observed they were not concern how the negligence of duty performance impact on the recovery of cardiac patient who need more intensive care after heart surgeries. Staff nurses of every shift makes dispute on handed and taking over the patient. The thing which hurt badly nurses think what is the benefit for make our duties perfectly and what is the effect of good performance on their salary. It shows they were just concerned to fulfill duty timing without any feeling of responsibly, empathy and even no feeling regret at any lost in sense of patient reintubation rate significantly increasing. Burnout lead to poor performance which increases the mortality rate of cardiac patients and in this sense the surgery cost bearing by government on each patient and whole effort of cardiac surgery team went into vain. That scenario put a lot of burden on me to think rationally and analyze the whole situation to find the cause and possible solution to change such nasty behavior of nurses, so, to overcome this issue for the sake of providing quality care to our little heart patient and make their speedy recovery sure.

Management Process:

As a Nurse Manager I am responsible and accountable for provision of quality care to my patient as well as providing most suitable, friendly and healthy environment which nurture nurses' self-esteem and job satisfaction. I do my best to handle the situation by using the steps of problem solving. Understand the causation of nurses Burnout and try to modify their behavior by compiling them in a professional relationship. Develop understanding of their nature of demands or expectation and start appraisal system which motivates them in positive manner to improve their performance.

Problem assessment:

ICU nurses burn out ratio significantly increasing due

to Wearisome working environment and issues, like, work overload, spending too much time in non-nursing task, lack of performance appraisal, lack of coherence, poor interpersonal relationship among staff etc. This affected the performance and disturbed the relationship among staff nurses. Ultimately decrease the productivity. Identify the problems which were faced by the staff nurses and interpersonal conflicts. Discuss the issues with all staff and built confidants among all to solve the interpersonal conflicts. Encourage the staff nurses with different strategies to improve the quality of performance.

Gather information:

Collect information by observing and taking feedback at different level and personally record the every possible reason behind each action and what interfere with teamwork.

Planning:

According to the above scenario: I prefer to apply the Positive Reinforcement theory and among them Maslow hierarchy of need theory as this is more suitable and beneficial according to above stated scenario.

According to Reinforcement theory behaviors learned through a process called operant conditioning in which a behavior becomes associated with a particular consequence. Consequences may be positive as with praise or recognition, or negative. Positive reinforces are used for the express purpose of increasing a desired behavior. Negative reinforces are used to inhibit an undesired behavior punished is common technique.

What motivate human behavior? A particular focus on human motivation include, incentive, satisfaction and intrinsic. Maslow hierarchy of needs theory is one of the best known theories of motivation. According to humanist psychologist Abraham Maslow, our action are motivated in order to achieve certain needs or goals. Motivation is such an important element of work productivity

Literature review:

The purpose of this literature review is to present an overview of these two theories that explain motivation in the workplace and address the factors that contribute to job satisfaction (motivation) or cause job dissatisfaction. A motive is what prompt a person to act in a certain way or at least develop an inclination for specific behavior (Markus, 2016).

A study to conducted the performance and reward

basis on investigate the main requirement for the effectiveness of a performance management system and purpose of performance and reward management practice (Shields et al., 2015).

Positive reinforcement aims to review the impact of positive reinforcement on the performances of employees in organizations. It can be applied by utilizing extrinsic rewards include salary, bonus and fringe benefit while intrinsic rewards are praise, encouragement and empowerment. By applying positive reinforcement in these factors, desired positive behaviors are encouraged and negative behaviors are eliminated. Financial and non-financial incentives have a positive relationship with the efficiency and effectiveness of staffs (Wei & Yazdanifard, 2014).

Another study concludes that there is positive relationship between rewards (extrinsic and intrinsic) and employee's job performance. Most of the organizations implement rewards system to increase the job performance and job satisfaction (Ibrar & Khan, 2015).

The use of financial and non-financial rewards plays an important role in nurses' perceived job attractiveness, and this leads to increased nurses' performance. Therefore, hospital officials should use non-monetary rewards in addition to financial rewards in their reward system. Financial and non-financial rewards have a significant effect on nurses' perceived job attractiveness and thus have a

significant effect on nursing job performance (Rahimi, Khalilipour, Bahmaei, Saberrad, & Torkashvand, 2017).

Maslow (1970, p. 195) argued humanistic education and motivation approach develop people who are strong and healthy with increased personal responsibilities in this way they have the potential to modify their behavior and action to change the society in which they live or work. According to Maslow work, achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement and growth are satisfier of human being, whereas, on the contrary company policy, supervision, working condition, interpersonal relations, salary, job security and personal life is person's dis-satisfiers (Sadri & Bowen, 2011).

Implementation (Management Theory application):

Improve the quality of performance by professional training and development session and counseling used to help nurses to identify the reason of their behaviors and share in sense of improvement not to embarrass and humiliate them. Moreover, engaging nurses in an optimistic relationship with their coworkers, listen their complain and take prompt action to resolve them, modify their behavior by positive reinforcement and discussion of thoughtful provoking events and experiences; appreciate their contribution in monthly meeting so that they trust on their employer and have a deep insight of their professional role and duties.

“Positive Reinforcement theories Model”

Create good understanding among ICU staff by giving them freedom of sharing their issues and concepts.

- Improve the skill performance of the staff through education session.
- Give reward to the staff nurses who try to do the best performance.
- Behavior modification through different strategies.
- Analyze the situation in all aspects and with the help of previous research study on this issue.
- Finding out the reason and logical points to solve this situation.
- Establish feedback system and workload measurement systems (WMSs).
- Create good understanding among ICU staff by giving them freedom of sharing their issues and concepts.
- Improve the skill performance of the staff through education session.
- Give reward to the staff nurses who try to do the best performance.
- Commit to clear, regular and precise communication.
- Acknowledge the importance of corporate work culture.

At the fourth level of Maslow hierarchy is the need for appreciation and respect, the esteem needs begin to play a vital role in motivating behavior, people have a need to accomplish things and have their effort recognized. In the form of appraisal gave them the sense that they are valued and feel they are making contribution in serving children suffering from congenital heart disease and surgery. Engaging

them in professional activities, academic accomplishment and team participation in this way they feel confident and empowered in their abilities. Self-actualized nurses will be well self-aware, concerned with personal as well as professional growth, less concerned with the opinion of others and ethically to maintain integrity and veracity in the professional relationship.

Evaluation:

Outcome of the application of this theory found to be very desirable. Therefore, nurses' job satisfaction and performance rate dramatically increased parallel. This also encourage the nurses' motivation to achieve departmental goal collaboratively with cardiac surgery team. And during this session they discovered that self-esteem and self-actualization strongly correlated with job satisfaction and happiness.

In this regard a study conducted in Iran on the "Predictors of happiness among Iranian Nurses" which result show by multiple regression analysis that there is a strong correlation with self-actualization and self-esteem with job satisfaction and happiness.(Khosrojerdi, Tagharrobi, Sooki, & Sharifi, 2018).

Learning:

It act as a reminder to me that this type of program is feasible and can be implemented frequently, it also has the potential to improve self-awareness among nurses and avoid conflict .By this practice we may reduce the economic burden on the patient and the health system.

**Maslow's Hierarchy of Need Theory Application
to manage nurses Burnout in CSICU**

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